

RA-QA: A Benchmarking System for Respiratory Audio Question Answering Under Real-World Heterogeneity

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Abstract

As conversational multimodal AI tools are increasingly adopted to process patient data for health assessment, robust benchmarks are needed to measure progress and expose failure modes under realistic conditions. Despite the importance of respiratory audio for mobile health screening, respiratory audio question answering remains underexplored, with existing studies evaluated narrowly and lacking real-world heterogeneity across modalities, devices, and question types. We hence introduce the **Respiratory-Audio Question-Answering (RA-QA) benchmark**, including a standardized data generation pipeline, a comprehensive multimodal QA collection, and a unified evaluation protocol. RA-QA harmonizes public RA datasets into a collection of 9 million format-diverse QA pairs covering diagnostic and contextual attributes. We benchmark classical ML baselines alongside multimodal audio-language models, establishing reproducible reference points and showing how current approaches fail under heterogeneity.

Index Terms: Respiratory health; Audio Question Answering; Multimodal Benchmark; Audio-Language Models; Healthcare.

1. Introduction

As large language models are increasingly used in clinical-facing settings, rigorous and realistic *benchmarks* have become essential to quantify both capabilities and failure modes under conditions that reflect real workflows (e.g., multi-turn, diverse users, and safety-critical criteria) [1]. Accordingly, evaluations should stress-test models across *diverse interaction styles* (e.g., question formats) and *real-world conditions* (e.g., heterogeneous contexts and recording devices), rather than assuming a single, static query and a homogeneous input setting [2].

Respiratory health is a particularly compelling setting for benchmark-driven evaluation: pulmonary and airway diseases remain a leading cause of global morbidity and mortality, and practical screening/monitoring tools must operate under noisy, heterogeneous real-world conditions (e.g., telemedicine and low-resource deployments) [3].

In clinical practice, auscultation is central to respiratory assessment: acoustic signatures such as wheezes, crackles, and abnormal timing patterns provide key diagnostic cues for conditions including asthma, pneumonia, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Recent advances in machine learning have achieved strong performance for respiratory sound classification from recordings [4, 5], and recent efforts have moved toward reusable respiratory foundations and standardized downstream evaluation [6], and multimodal audio-text

Figure 1: RA-QA question formats: the same respiratory audio recording is queried as open-ended, multiple-choice, or single-verify (yes/no), each requiring a different answer style.

models for respiratory outcome prediction [7]. However, most prior work treats respiratory audio as a *single-output prediction* problem, producing a predefined label or score per recording (e.g., diagnosis or symptom presence), rather than supporting question-conditioned, conversational answering.

In realistic patient-facing and clinical workflows, respiratory assessment is inherently *question-driven*: users and clinicians may ask diverse, context-dependent questions about the same recording, such as verifying a symptom, probing diagnostic consistency, estimating severity, or querying acquisition conditions. Questions also come in multiple answer formats (e.g., binary, multiple-choice, numeric, or free-form). Supporting these interactions requires models that jointly interpret respiratory audio and a natural-language query and produce clinically grounded responses, rather than a single static label.

While question answering (QA) has been extensively benchmarked for other clinical modalities (EHR, imaging, biosignals), including large-scale resources for text QA [8, 9, 10] and multimodal QA for imaging and signals [11, 12, 13], respiratory audio-grounded QA remains comparatively under-benchmarked. In parallel, general audio-language models [14, 15, 16] enable broad audio understanding and open generation from paired audio-text inputs, but they are not designed or systematically evaluated for subtle auscultation cues, disease-specific semantics, and distribution shifts typical of real respira-

tory recordings. Even though recent respiratory QA efforts have advanced, they are limited in scope or availability: CaReQA/CaReSound [17] is a valuable step toward medical audio QA, but does not comprehensively cover the variability encountered in respiratory assessment across cough/breath/speech modalities, heterogeneous recording conditions and devices, diverse diseases and attributes, and multiple QA formats under a unified evaluation protocol.

To address this gap, we introduce **Respiratory-Audio Question-Answering (RA-QA)**, a publicly available benchmarking system for respiratory audio QA. RA-QA (i) provides a standardized generation pipeline for QA pairs generation from existing datasets, (ii) harmonizes multiple public respiratory audio corpora into a large-scale collection of 9 million question-answer pairs spanning diagnostic and contextual attributes across modalities and question formats (Figure 1), (iii) benchmarks both traditional audio ML baselines and general audio-language generation models under a common protocol, enabling systematic and reproducible comparison, and (iv) shows that general audio-language models and generic audio benchmarks do not reliably transfer to subtle respiratory cues, and that semantic similarity can remain high despite low task-level correctness, motivating evaluation that jointly reports semantic fidelity and task-level performance. The full generation code and the released QA pairs are publicly available at <https://anonymous.4open.science/r/RA-QA-6CB3/>.

2. RA-QA Data Curation

The RA-QA pipeline converts heterogeneous respiratory audio datasets into a unified, QA-ready benchmark by harmonizing clinical attributes, standardizing metadata, and automatically generating natural language question-answer pairs. It explicitly operationalizes a dataset-to-QA transformation process, enabling reproducible conversion of diverse respiratory datasets into a unified multimodal QA format. This design ensures consistency, scalability, and interoperability across diverse data sources and clinical contexts.

2.1. RA-QA collection design

The RA-QA benchmark comprises over 9 million question-answer pairs generated from 11 distinct datasets [18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28] encompassing multiple respiratory conditions (e.g., asthma, COPD, COVID-19) and covering a wide range of respiratory audio types, including cough, breathing, speech, and auscultation recordings. Table 1 summarizes dataset-level statistics. Several datasets include multiple recordings per participant, collected under different conditions or time points, introducing longitudinal variability that supports patient-specific modeling. Moreover, some datasets provide segment-level labels within the same recording, enabling finer-grained analysis of respiratory events and localized acoustic phenomena. Since some labels are clinically validated and others are self-reported, the resulting diversity in recording conditions and metadata reflects realistic deployment scenarios and supports the development of robust, generalizable respiratory audio QA systems.

We categorize RA-QA targets into four macro-attribute categories that capture complementary clinical signals: (i) acoustic features, including segment-level annotations that support multiple clinically grounded questions per recording and reflect temporal or spatial variability in respiratory sounds; (ii) con-

Figure 2: Overview of the RA-QA dataset creation pipeline.

sultation context, describing symptoms and testing status at the time of recording; (iii) demographics and health profile, providing background clinical context; and (iv) recording context, encoding environmental and procedural factors that influence audio characteristics. Together, these categories encourage models to reason not only over clinically relevant context but also over respiratory acoustics. Meanwhile, RA-QA spans two task families: *discriminative* tasks, where the answer is a categorical label (e.g., diagnosis/symptom presence), and *regression* tasks, where the answer is a continuous numeric value (e.g., physiological measurements).

RA-QA system QA pairs are developed according to three formats: (i) open-ended (OE) questions, which expect free-text responses without predefined options, simulating natural dialogue, (ii) multiple-choice (MC) questions, which follow the same structure as open-ended ones but include a set of suggested answer options within the prompt, following a prompt-engineering approach, and (iii) single-verify (SV) questions, limited to binary responses. The three formats have been developed to increase the contextual and linguistic diversity of the dataset, enabling models, particularly large language models, to better interpret semantically equivalent prompts that may vary in structure or phrasing. This diversity helps simulate real-world scenarios where users (clinicians or patients) might pose questions in different formats.

2.2. RA-QA generation pipeline

A robust pipeline was designed and implemented to uniformly process the diverse datasets (see Figure 2) to ensure a harmonized and standardized QA collection, thus achieving consistency across the benchmark. The processing workflow was divided into several stages:

Metadata Standardization and Label Mapping. The first stage of dataset processing focused on standardizing the metadata across the 11 source datasets to ensure consistency in structure and interpretation. As part of the QA formatting process, original categorical labels were systematically mapped to descriptive text strings. While some interpretative decisions were required, they were guided by established clinical terminology and dataset documentation.

Template Structuring. From each standardized metadata file, JSON-based question templates were generated for all relevant attributes. According to the design choice reported in Section 2.1, we defined three question-format templates: open-ended questions, multiple-choice questions, and single-verify

Table 1: Overview statistics of the generated respiratory-audio RA-QA collection.

	KAUH	Coswara	CoughVID	COVID-19 Sounds	HF Lung	ICBHI	MM Lung	NoseMic	Resp@TR	SSBPR	UK COVID-19	All
Number of Audio Samples	336	24860	1855	2046	9765	6895	80	1297	504	7569	213492	268699
Mean duration (s)	17.40	9.85	8.37	14.33	15.00	2.70	7.77	30.00	21.75	2.36	6.29	6.86
Mean Question Length	11.02	7.71	7.83	8.62	11.06	9.72	8.34	7.50	10.47	10.00	8.79	8.78
Number of Unique Questions	30	38	37	47	9	25	10	6	12	12	48	207
Mean Answer Length	6.88	6.71	5.99	8.24	8.49	5.58	6.12	6.17	7.96	7.97	4.90	5.09
Number of Unique Answers	136	146	164	637	20	243	153	620	29	32	232129	234064
QA Pairs	9033	430473	76450	59187	55255	171849	680	7782	5544	90828	8089056	8996137

questions. Templates are instantiated with natural-language question prompts and paired with human-readable answers, such that each instance forms an actual QA exchange rather than a raw label prediction. For regression-valued attributes, we generate open-ended templates only, as enumerating numeric options would have been impractical, whereas for discriminative attributes we instantiate all applicable question types.

QA Pair Generation. Once the templates and standardized metadata were defined, QA pairs were programmatically generated for each individual patient in the datasets. This resulted in a collection of personalized question-answer pairs, where each question targets specific metadata fields (e.g., symptoms, diagnosis, age) and each answer is drawn from the corresponding patient data. These QA pairs are then associated with the patients’ respiratory audio recordings, creating a multimodal instance that links textual input, audio context, and textual output. This patient-level generation strategy ensures that the resulting dataset is coherent, scalable, and suitable for training and evaluating multimodal QA systems in respiratory health contexts. Assigned splits followed the original dataset protocols when available; otherwise, stratified splits were applied based on other available attributes. Data were partitioned into 70/15/15 train/validation/test splits.

3. RA-QA Baseline Benchmarking

RA-QA benchmarking provides baseline evaluations for respiratory audio question answering. Our goal is to quantify (i) how much clinically relevant information can be recovered from respiratory acoustics and question text in isolation, and (ii) how well general multimodal models transfer to clinically grounded respiratory QA. To this end, we benchmark both *unimodal machine learning baselines* and *multimodal* models.

3.1. Baselines

In the benchmark, we include both naive baselines (majority and random guessing), unimodal baseline (audio-only), and multimodal baselines, including a general audio-language model and an existing respiratory audio QA model.

Majority baseline. We include a majority-label predictor that outputs the most frequent training label for each target. This baseline mirrors the class imbalance present in many RA-QA attributes, and provides a reference for how much performance can be obtained from label priors alone.

Random baseline. As a chance-level reference, the random baseline samples uniformly from the valid label set for each target. It is most informative for diagnosing whether a method improves beyond chance in settings with many labels, and for contextualizing performance on balanced or near-balanced attributes. We repeat sampling over 5 random seeds and report the mean.

Audio-only baseline. To isolate what can be recovered from acoustics alone, we train an SVM audio-only classifier [29].

This baseline quantifies the extent to which clinically relevant attributes are encoded in respiratory audio without any access to the question intent, but is dataset- and task-specific.

Multimodal classifier. To measure the benefit of conditioning on the question, we train a simple late-fusion classifier that embeds the audio with OPERA-CT and the question with a fixed text encoder, concatenates the two embeddings, and predicts the target with an MLP. This baseline tests whether question information helps disambiguate the intended attribute and answer format when the same recording supports multiple queries. For *regression-valued* attributes, the same architecture uses a scalar regression head.

General audio-language baseline. Finally, we evaluate Pengi [14] as a representative general-purpose audio-language model to assess how far a strong pretrained generative system transfers to respiratory QA without domain-specific fine-tuning. Pengi is prompted with the paired input (x, q) and generates a free-form answer, which we subsequently normalize/parse for task-level scoring. We use Pengi in a zero-shot setting, with beam search (beam size = 3), temperature = 1.0, maximum generation length = 30 tokens, and batch size = 8.

CaReQA-style generative baseline. We include a domain-trained generative *audio-to-LLM* baseline inspired by CaReQA [17], which maps medical-audio embeddings into the language model space and injects them as a soft prefix for decoder-only generation. We encode each recording with a frozen OPERA-CT backbone to obtain audio embeddings and a GPT-2 text embedder for text embeddings.

3.2. Evaluation Metrics

RA-QA answers can be evaluated along two complementary axes: *linguistic correctness*, which measures how closely a predicted answer matches the reference in wording and meaning (i.e., surface form and semantics), and *clinical correctness*, which measures whether the prediction corresponds to the correct underlying clinical label or numeric value, and therefore whether the system is clinically reliable. To capture both aspects, we use two metrics: a *text-level* metric for linguistic fidelity and a *task-level* metric for clinical correctness.

Semantic level metric. Semantic correctness (text-level fidelity) is intended to capture whether a system produces an answer that is linguistically well-formed and semantically aligned with the reference, even when multiple phrasings are acceptable. In this paper, we report **BERTScore** [30], highlighting whether predictions preserve the intended meaning beyond exact lexical overlap.

Label-correctness metric. Clinical relevance is assessed at the *task level* by extracting the underlying target from the generated answer and treating it as a label. In this paper, we report **MacroF1 score** for discriminative tasks. For *regression* targets, clinical correctness is naturally expressed as numeric error, thus we report **MAE** (mean absolute error), which quantifies the average deviation between predicted and ground-truth values.

Table 2: Global baseline performance on RA-QA: MacroF1 / BERTScore for discriminative tasks (by question type) and MAE / BERTScore for regression ones (open-ended only). Values are rounded to two decimals; Pengi’s task-level scores are often orders of magnitude below 10^{-2} and therefore appear as 0.00 after rounding. BERTScore is not reported for the multimodal classifier.

Task	Question Types	Reference Baselines			Multimodal Baselines		
		Random	Majority	Audio only	Pengi	Multimodal Classifier	CareAQA-style
Discriminative	Single-verify	0.10 / 0.98	0.49 / 0.99	0.49 / 0.86	0.46 / 0.38	0.59 / 0.95	0.51 / 0.95
	Open-ended	0.09 / 0.92	0.19 / 0.92	0.49 / 0.89	0.00 / 0.57	0.11 / 0.96	0.11 / 0.96
	Multiple-choice	0.10 / 0.92	0.22 / 0.93	0.57 / 0.81	0.00 / 0.68	0.12 / 0.95	0.16 / 0.96
Regressive	Open-ended	10.32 / 0.95	7.84 / 0.95	10.50 / -0.10	N/A / N/A	8.06 / N/A	9.53 / 0.96

3.3. Evaluation setup

We construct a label-balanced subset (with sampling performed *within each attribute*) with a patient-wise split, using $\approx 100,000$ QA instances for training, $\approx 15,000$ for validation, and $\approx 15,000$ for testing. Since a single recording can support multiple questions, for *unimodal* baselines we treat each attribute as an independent classification task, including regressive ones. In contrast, *multimodal* baselines are evaluated on the full subset.

4. Results

Unimodal baselines. Table 2 reports random/majority as lower-bound references and shows that the dataset- and task-specific audio-only baseline substantially improves over these priors, especially for open-ended and multiple-choice discriminative questions (MacroF1 0.49 and 0.57), indicating an *informative* respiratory acoustic signal. We note that audio-only is an oracle-style reference that requires training many specialized models (per attribute/dataset/question type), which is operationally unrealistic; we include it as an upper bound on what acoustics alone, without question conditioning, can achieve.

General audio-language transfer. The general audio-language baseline, Pengi, transfers poorly to RA-QA, with near-zero task-level MacroF1 on open-ended and multiple-choice discriminative questions and low BERTScore overall (Table 2). Qualitatively, Pengi often defaults to generic audio event descriptions rather than producing question-conditioned, attribute-specific answers. This behavior is consistent with its captioning-oriented training objective and highlights the need for question-conditioned models and benchmarks tailored to clinically grounded respiratory audio QA, rather than relying on generic audio captioning transfer.

Trained multimodal baselines. Both the multimodal classifier and the CaReAQA-style generative baseline were trained jointly on the pooled RA-QA subset, mixing datasets, attributes, and question types. Compared to Pengi, the multimodal classifier yields markedly higher discriminative MacroF1 (0.59 on single-verify), showing that question conditioning helps disambiguate intent under heterogeneous data; however, it is non-generative and thus limited to predicting canonical targets rather than producing free-form answers. The CaReAQA-style model improves over zero-shot transfer and attains a strong BERTScore (up to 0.96), indicating that respiratory-trained audio-to-LLM alignment is beneficial, but task-level performance remains modest on open-ended and multiple-choice questions. Overall, these results underline the benchmark’s core challenge: handling RA-QA’s heterogeneity requires models that jointly optimize semantic fidelity *and* task-level correctness.

Case studies. To further analyze benchmark behavior beyond aggregate scores, we report two representative cases summarized in Table 3. For case (1), we report results on ICBHI *diag-*

nosis tasks, which show that baseline ranking depends strongly on question format: the CaReAQA-style model performs best on open-ended and multiple-choice, whereas the discriminative multimodal classifier leads on single-verify. This flip suggests that different model families exploit different aspects of the QA interface, with generative audio-to-LLM pipelines advantaged when producing free-form or option-conditioned text, and discriminative fusion more stable when the task reduces to a constrained yes/no decision. For case (2), we analyze *exhalation SNR* (Table 3) from the self-reported dataset UK COVID-19. Pengi again fails to produce usable task answers (N/A), consistent with captioning-style transfer not aligning to attribute-specific queries. Among trained baselines, the CaReAQA-style model is competitive with the multimodal classifier on the regressive attribute (MAE 0.08 vs. 0.06) while maintaining high semantic fidelity (BERTScore 0.94). This suggests that question-conditioned generation can be robust to self-recorded variability, motivating stronger generative baselines for continuous targets under RA-QA heterogeneity, which can remain competitive with classification methods while retaining the advantage of natural-language expression.

Table 3: Case-studies results by question type (SV / OE / MC). Each cell reports task score (MacroF1 or MAE) / BERTScore.

Case	QT	Multimodal classifier	Pengi	CareAQA-style
Case 1	SV	0.45 / 0.99	0.13 / 0.82	0.46 / 0.99
	OE	0.07 / 0.94	0.00 / 0.80	0.14 / 0.96
	MC	0.09 / 0.86	0.00 / 0.80	0.33 / 0.85
Case 2	SV	0.06 / N/A	N/A / N/A	0.08 / 0.94

5. Conclusion

We introduced **RA-QA**, an open-source *collection and benchmarking system* for respiratory audio question answering, comprising a standardized data-curation pipeline, leakage-aware splits, and a unified evaluation protocol. RA-QA is designed to stress-test models under realistic heterogeneity, including multiple question formats over the same recording; diverse modalities and datasets/devices; and both discriminative and regression targets across four attribute families. Baseline results show that RA-QA’s heterogeneity exposes the limited robustness of current approaches and that high semantic similarity can still coincide with low task-level clinical correctness, motivating heterogeneity-aware respiratory-audio QA models that jointly optimize linguistic fidelity and prediction accuracy. By releasing RA-QA as a reproducible benchmarking system, we aim to enable fair comparisons under heterogeneity, and to support the development of respiratory-specific, question-conditioned models that are both linguistically well-formed and task-correct.

6. References

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